

Agroforestry in Galicia

Stakeholders Policy challenges

- Inventory of problems for each region and how were it solved
- Factsheets: current policy an AF at regional level
- Digitalization, useful tools, funding of these systems from administration.
- Bureaucracy: management and processing usually at slow pace, administrative forms tedious.
- Legal framework non dynamic. Regulation not adapted to new productive and processing models.

Policy recommendations

- 1.- Development of working groups to fit funds to existing challenges, reduce bureaucracy at minimum and adapt the legal framework for agroforestry practices implementation in both forest and agricultural land uses.
- 2.- Develop advisory systems linked to global and local research.
- 3.- Establish a short, intermediate and long term strategy to ensure agroforestry transition based on knowledge and digitalization.
- 4.- Understanding agroforestry as a land management ecosystem services provider and a value chain promotion linked to the use of the territory.
- 5.- Better understanding between the different ministries (i.e. environment and agriculture).

STATE:	Spain		Agrisilviculture	0,03%	0,22%
Nut level:	2		Agrosilvopasture	0,00%	0,00%
Eurostat code:	ES11		Home gardens	0,59%	0,83%
Area (km ²):	29.375		Holding type	2016	2023
Population	2018	2022	Natural person (ha)	483.980	-
Population	2.703.048	2.692.829	Legal person (ha)	134.560	-
Density (p km ⁻²)	92	92	Group holding and Common land unit (ha)	-	-
Cover data	2018	2022	Natural person (holder)	72.570	-
Forest	40,02%	27,15%	Legal person (holder)	3.800	-
Arable land	9,10%	12,66%	Group holding and Common land unit (holder)	-	-
Permanent crops	0,34%	0,30%	Regional Used Agricultural Area	2016	2023
Agroforestry	6,05%	8,92%	Farm number	76.360	-
Shrubland	16,24%	12,53%	Farm ha (UAA)	618.540	-
Grassland	18,44%	28,50%	Animal populations (Thousand head)	2018	2023
Agroforestry Practice Cover	2018	2022			
Silvopasture	5,43%	7,88%			

Live bovine animals	935	941
Dairy cows	341	337
Non dairy cows	204	204
Live swine, domestic species	1.201	1.627
Live sheep	204	150
Live goats	51	38

CROPS (Hectares) 2016 2023

Utilised agricultural area	618.540	-
Cereals for the production of grain (including seed)	36.160	-
Common wheat and spelt	11.970	-
Durum wheat	3.330	-
Rye and winter cereal mixtures (maslin)	3.380	-
Barley	580	-
Oats and spring cereal mixtures	190	-
Grain maize and corn-cob-mix	15.780	-
Rice	-	-
Dry pulses and protein crops for the production of grain	590	-
Industrial crops	30	-
Cotton seed and fibre	-	-
Other oilseed crops n.e.c.	-	-
Fibre crops	-	-
Aromatic, medicinal and culinary plants	-	-
Plants harvested green from arable land	117.090	-
Green maize	66.070	-
Kitchen gardens	330	-

Rural Development Interventions promoting agroforestry

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ENVCLIM(70) - Environmental, climate-related and other management commitments

Interventions	3
Forestry	2
Crop diversification including woody perennials	0
Crop rotation including woody perennials	2
Livestock including woody perennials	0
Woody perennials to reduce soil erosion	0
Woody perennials to add organic matter	0
Woody perennials to reduce soil chemical contamination	0
Animal welfare using woody perennials	0
Permanent Grasslands with woody perennials	0
Agroforestry on Permanent Crops	0
Interventions	3

References

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- Key farm variables area livestock (LSU) labour force and standard output (SO) by agricultural size of farm (UAA) legal status of holding and NUTS 2 regions (ef_kvaareg) https://doi.org/10.2908/EF_KVAAREG
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